

VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
GLOBAL PARTNERSHIP

Identifying factors impacting fisher relations with co-management institutions: a case study in Satkhira, the Bangladesh Sundarbans

V2V Working Paper No. 2025-08

Akash Kar

September 2025

Working Paper Series Editors:

Prateep Kumar Nayak

School of Environment, Enterprise and Development (SEED), Faculty of Environment, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada

Derek Armitage

School of Environment, Resources and Sustainability (SERS), Faculty of Environment, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada

Publication design and formatting:

Maha Abdelbaset and Farosat Alamshoeva

School of Environment, Enterprise and Development, Faculty of Environment, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada

Cover photo:

Md. Ruyel Miah

School of Environment, Enterprise and Development, Faculty of Environment, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada

How to cite:

Kar A. (2025). *Identifying factors impacting fisher relations with co-management institutions: a case study in Satkhira, the Bangladesh Sundarbans*. V2V Working Paper 2025-08 V2V Global Partnership, University of Waterloo, Canada. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17122378>.

V2V Global Partnership Secretariat
School of Environment, Enterprise and Development,
Faculty of Environment
200 University Avenue West, EV 3
University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, N2L 3G1 Canada
Website: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org
Email: v2vglobalpartnership@gmail.com

V2V Global Partnership is supported by the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada under its Partnership Grant Program.

Social Sciences and Humanities
Research Council of Canada

Conseil de recherches en
sciences humaines du Canada

Canada

V2V Working Paper Series

V2V Global Partnership “Working Paper Series” aims to facilitate the exchange of ideas, mobilize knowledge, and generate broad-based discussions on vulnerability-viability themes within the context of small-scale fisheries. The Working Paper Series will provide a collaborative and interactive platform for academics, practitioners, representatives of civil society, and individuals interested in making written contributions to the theoretical, methodological, practical, and policy aspects of small-scale fisheries, both locally and globally. To contribute to the V2V Working Paper Series, please contact v2vglobalpartnership@gmail.com.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	1
2. Methodology and case study area.....	2
2.1 Methodology.....	2
2.1.1. Measuring reach.....	3
2.1.2. Measuring transparency.....	3
2.1.3. Measuring empowerment.....	3
2.2 Case-study area.....	3
3. Results.....	5
3.1. Cross Union Comparison.....	5
3.1.1 Reach.....	5
3.1.2 Institutional Transparency.....	6
3.1.3 Institutional Empowerment.....	7
3.2. Cross Stakeholder Comparison.....	8
3.2.1 Multi-Stakeholder Data.....	8
4. Discussion.....	9
4.1 Fisher accounts.....	10
4.1.1 Reach, transparency and empowerment.....	10
4.2 Multi-Stakeholder Accounts.....	11
4.2.1 Class Issues and Lack of Social Capital.....	11
4.2.2 Corruption.....	12
4.2.3 Loan.....	13
4.2.4 Knowledge-Sharing.....	13
5. Conclusions.....	14
References.....	15

Identifying factors impacting fisher relations with co-management institutions: a case study in Satkhira, the Bangladesh Sundarbans

Akash Kar^{1*}

¹ V2V Global Partnership, Faculty of Environment, University of Waterloo, Canada

* Corresponding authors: akash.kar@uwaterloo.ca

Abstract

Small-scale fisheries provide immense social-ecological value to Bangladesh and exist as a significant component of the national economy. Despite their importance, small-scale fishers in Bangladesh remain amongst the most vulnerable populations in the world. Not only do fishers deal with food insecurity, poor water access, little education opportunity, limited access to healthcare, among a variety of other traits limiting the social mobility of fishers, but fishing itself as a practice has become less viable over time. Small-scale fishers have been impacted by increased competition, decreased fish stock, poor regulation, and a rapidly changing ecology, among other conditions, which make small-scale fishing practices vulnerable. These conditions are consistent throughout the country; however, specifically in the Sundarbans, they are amplified. Originally adopted to increase local participation in decision-making processes, community-based management institutions were introduced to Bangladesh in the late 1990s and officially came to the Sundarbans in 2009. This study aims to analyze stakeholder interactions in the current co-management structures present in Satkhira, the largest district of the Sundarbans, to better understand how the institutions work to impact small-scale fishers and their livelihood practices. Case studies were conducted in four unions in Satkhira, and a legal pluralism framework was applied in the fifth chapter to contextualize the relationships between statutory and customary institutions. This study found reach to be a relevant measurement when analyzing co-management institutions and further found a relationship between the factors of reach, transparency, and empowerment. The findings of this study further support that strong legal pluralism is unlikely through neoliberal conservation.

Keywords Small-scale fisheries • co-management • Sundarbans • legal pluralism • Vulnerability • Viability

1. Introduction

The social and economic influence of fisheries in Bangladesh is representative of a complex relationship between nation and resource that has developed over centuries. Bangladesh has a unique geography shaped by near-by river deltas, which promote highly fertile agriculture and fishing lands (Rahman, 2011). This has allowed Bangladesh to become self-sufficient in several key food items while simultaneously allowing the country to become a world leader in agricultural and fisheries production (Islam, 2023). In 2022, Bangladesh had the seventh largest fisheries harvest in the world, producing over 4,915,000 tonnes of capture and aquaculture (DOF, 2023). In the 2021-22 fiscal year fish accounted for over 1% of Bangladesh's total export earnings and over 3.5% of the nation's total GDP (Hossain, 2023; Azad & Azad, 2022). The fishing industry contributes to over ¼ of the agriculture GDP, a sector which employs over 40% of the country's labour force (Islam, 2023; International Trade Administration, 2022). Domestically, fish is the predominant protein source and particular species such as hilsa are heavily ingrained in Bangladeshi culture. Despite the significance of their labour to the nation's economy, and culture, natural resource workers are amongst the poorest people in Bangladesh. Agriculture workers, and fishers specifically, typically live in

marginalized conditions and often fail to access adequate food, water, education, and healthcare services. For example, in Bangladesh less than 15% of occupational fishers are literate (Diba et al, 2022).

The Sundarbans falls between India and Bangladesh and is perhaps best known for hosting one of the world's largest concentrations of Bengal tigers. The forest is the largest mangrove forest in the world and home to over 3.5 million resource-dependent forest dwellers in Bangladesh (Islam & Shamsuddoha, 2018). The forest falls in the south-west corner of the nation, acting as a wall of protection to the rest of the nation from the storms, harsh waters, and natural disasters which stem from the Bay of Bengal (Granek & Ruttenberg, 2007; Barbier, 2016; Badola & Hussain, 2005). Bangladesh's coastline is amongst the most dangerous in the world and has hosted over 70 major cyclones in the last 200 years (Saha, 2015). The Sundarbans represents tremendous ecological, economic, and cultural significance for Bangladesh, as such, the deforestation and deterioration of the Sundarbans should be considered a significant threat to the nation's safety.

The forest is the nation's largest source for lumber resources, and a large contributor to the nation's fisheries industry (Shamsuzzaman et al., 2020; Roy & Alam, 2012). The forest is renowned for non-lumber goods as well, such as honey, and is significant for its contributions to the wider agricultural industry. Despite the productivity of the land, the forest is going through significant ecological change. Natural processes such as erosion have decreased forest lands by over 2.5% from the 1990's to the 2000's (Giri et al., 2014). Growing human settlements, industries, exploitation of forest resources, as well as environmental catastrophes such as cyclones and oil spills have contributed to significant forest loss over the years (Rahman, 2009). This has impacted forest-dwellers and the viability of their livelihood practices, forcing the migration of tens of thousands of resource-dependent people in the forest (Gunjal, 2021). Community-based governance, or co-management institutions were introduced to the forest in 2009 to promote the viability of forest resources and forest-dwellers (Begum et al., 2021). These institutions involve community members in decision-making in hopes to better incorporate local knowledge with managing processes. This paper outlines factors identified in stakeholder responses as common themes associated with the vulnerability and viability of small-scale fishers and their livelihood practices as they relate to the co-management institutions.

2. Methodology and case study area

2.1 Methodology

This study used a phenomenological approach to reveal common themes found in interview data. The results were broken into two sections. In the first section, common themes across the four selected unions were identified using fisher data. Reach, transparency, and empowerment were identified as prevalent themes in the data and the three factors were analyzed to better understand their relationships between themselves. Three ranking systems ranging from scores 0-3 were established for the three fisher-identified themes. The second section identified themes of social capital, corruption, fisher dependency on loans, and knowledge-sharing using both fisher and non-fisher data as the largest factors which impact fisher livelihoods and their participation in co-management institutions.

The secondary section reviewed the prevalence of several factors as they were found in interview data. This data focused on factors which impact the relationship of small-scale fishers and the co-management institutions. This was done to better understand the livelihood impacts of fishers as they are related to the co-management institutions. This section did not measure reach, transparency, or empowerment as it was covered in the previous section.

2.1.1. Measuring reach

1. Has not been consulted by or has not heard of the current co-management institutions.
2. Is aware but has not attended any meetings.
3. Is aware and attends/has attended a meeting.

2.1.2. Measuring transparency

1. A score of 0 representing identification of corruption, briberies, illegal activities, or a lack of reach or communication towards fishing stakeholders.
2. A score of 1 represents knowledge-sharing or other information-based interactions, however fishers have primarily a listening role and do not have considerable knowledge about the rules of institutions.
3. A score of 2 represents identification of either fisher interactions with good information, fishers have a role beyond listening only, or fishers having a basic understanding of the goals of the institutions.
4. A score of 3 represents fisher interactions with good information, where fishers have more than a mere listening role, where fishers have the ability to access further institutional information, where stakeholders have a clear idea of the purpose, rules, and regulations of the institutions and are able to effectively communicate within the institutions.

2.1.3. Measuring empowerment

1. A score of 0 represents a complete lack in interactions, or a lack of adequate living conditions negatively impacting the fishers desire to engage in the institutions. This represents fishers who lack the empowerment to initially engage with the institutions.
2. A score of 1 represents that stakeholders have interacted with the institutions or have adequate living conditions which empower them to engage with the institutions. This represents fishers who lack empowerment to adequately engage in the institutions but still have had interactions.
3. A score of 2 represents that fishers have access to and are able to take advantage of institutional resources which benefit the viability of fishers and their families. A score of 2 is meant to represent increased fisher communication within the institutions leading to an increased decision-making ability for fishing stakeholders. A score of 2 is meant to represent a partial fisher agency, where fishers' initiatives or decision-making are heavily influenced by other stakeholders in the institutions.
4. A score of 3 represents fishers that have taken advantage of and benefited from institutional resources. A score of 3 is meant to represent a fully empowered fisher, whose interactions with the co-management institutions are mutually beneficial to both the fisher and other stakeholders, where fishers have full agency in decision-making. A score of 3 is meant to represent the self-organization of fisher initiatives or decision-making leading to improved livelihood conditions, supported by the co-management institutions.

2.2 Case-study area

This study focused on the co-management institutions in the Sundarbans, focused specifically on the Satkhira range. To do so, four unions were selected from the Shyamnagar upazila. Shyamnagar is home to over 350,000 individuals and is the largest upazila in Bangladesh (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, 2023). It is the south-western corner of the country, bordering West Bengal to the west and the Bay of Bengal to the south. The area is vulnerable to natural disaster due to its environmentally volatile location as well as man-made interference (Giri et al., 2014; Rahman, 2009). The literacy rate in the area is 48.6% with a stark gendered difference, which is nearly 30% below the national average (Islam, 2016; World Bank, 2024). The two largest employment types in the region are agriculture (32.93%), agricultural workers (25.81%),

followed by ‘other’ (12.3%) (Didar-UI et al., 2015). Wage labourer (6.21%), and fishing (5.5%) were not far behind. The people of Shyamnagar are significant for the maintenance of the forest and exist as a significant portion of the forest’s labour force. 53 interviews involving fishers and non-fishers were conducted and analyzed. A map of the Shyamnagar upazila which identifies the four unions selected for this study is available directly below, as figure 1. The study sites were selected using four criteria. Unions were selected based on if they had past and current co-management institutions, whether they hosted a significant small-scale fishing population, their proximity to both each other and the forest, and personal ease to travel. The four selected unions can be seen below on figure 1.

Figure 1

Shyamnagar upazila map

Source: Prepared by Local Government Engineering Department

3. Results

As mentioned, the results are split into two sections. Institutional reach, transparency, and empowerment emerged as three prevalent themes when reading fisher data. Reach was measured as it was evident that fishers had different levels of interactions with the institutions. Transparency was measured as it was evident that fishers lacked trust in governing institutions. Empowerment was measured to understand fishers perceived livelihood benefits as provided by the institutions. These themes were analyzed and ranked from a scale of 0-3, across all four unions. These measurements are represented in the first section. The second section uses fisher and non-fisher data to understand the dominant perceptions of factors which impact fisher livelihoods as they relate to the co-management institutions. Figure 2 outlines institutional reach throughout the four unions. Figure 3 outlines transparency throughout the four unions. Figure 4 outlines empowerment throughout the four unions. Table 1 outlines factors selected by fishers and non-fishers as impacts to fisher livelihood. Figure 5 compares fisher and non-fisher responses. Figure 6 represents the relationship between the factors of reach, transparency, and empowerment. The six figures and table are available below. An analysis of the results is available in the discussion section.

3.1. Cross Union Comparison

3.1.1 Reach

Figure 2

Institutional Reach

Reach of Co-Management Institutions

Source: Author's creation

Institutional reach was consistent among unions, except for Burigoalini where significantly more fishers were interacting with the institutions. Munigonj, Gabura, and Koikali were uniform with the biggest percentage of users responding that they hadn't heard of or been consulted about the institutions, while the second largest groups were those aware of the institutions, and the smallest group were those who were aware of the institutions but have yet to attend a meeting. When considering unaware fishers, all unions except for Burigoalini fell within a 6% difference of 50%, within a range of 47-56%. Burigoalini was an extreme outlier, measuring 27%. 46% of fishers' in Burigoalini had reported that they had been to a co-management meeting, 13% higher than the next highest union. Burigoalini was the only union where the majority of interviewees responded that they had been to a meeting before. The remaining unions answered between 27-33%.

3.1.2 Institutional Transparency

Figure 3

Measurement of Institutional Transparency

Transparency of Governing Actors within Co-Management Institutions

Source: Author's creation

Similar to the first measurement, fishers in Burigoalini existed as something of an outlier when measuring institutional transparency. Across all unions, results showed that fishers are primarily split within two groups, one slightly smaller group representing a complete lack of transparency (46.67%), and one slightly larger group (48.89%) representing early stages of institutional transparency. Only a handful of fishers in Burigoalini felt favourably when considering how transparent co-management systems are, which accounted for 4.44% of total responses. Generally, within the co-management institutions, small-scale fishers have little sway and influence. Through interviews, fishers showed frustration with their ability, or lack of ability, to communicate within the co-management institutions. Related, some fishers felt that co-management institutions are a waste of time.

3.1.3 Institutional Empowerment

Figure 4

Fisher Empowerment

Determining Fisherman Empowerment Within Current Institutions

Source: Author's creation

100% of fishers recorded a score of 0, or 1. Just under 49% of fishers recorded a score of 0, while just over 51% of fishers recorded a score of 1. When considering the first three unions without Burigoalini, 58.33% of fishers recorded a score of zero, and 41.67% of fishers recorded a score of 1. There were no fishers that recorded a score of 2 or 3. This not only indicates that no fishers feel that their input has been implemented, but no fishers felt that they are listened to in the co-management institutions at all. Beyond this, no fishers fell into the category of having clean water and food, access to education, and adequate sanitation systems. It should be noted that the disparity between these factors differs between fishers and unions, and some fishers do interact with higher levels of food, water, sanitation and education, no fishers qualified for this score as they better identified with a score between 0-1. While Burigoalini continuously has produced more favourable results when compared with the other three unions, no fishers in Burigoalini reported that they felt listened to. Meaning that the empowerment of fishers in the union that has consistently been scoring the highest on all measurements thus far, is in its early stage of empowerment building at best.

3.2. Cross-Stakeholder Comparison

This section overviews the stakeholder data from fisher and non-fisher stakeholder groups. It attempts to outline factors identified by all groups to paint a holistic understanding of all stakeholders' perceptions of institutional factors which impact small-scale fishers.

3.2.1 Multi-Stakeholder Data

Table 1	
<i>Named factors</i>	
All Stakeholder Responses	Total Percentile
Class	15.20%
Corruption	15.20%
Loan	13.60%
Knowledge-sharing	12.80%
Disorganization of Institution / No fishing records	7.20%
No consultation	6.40%
Decreasing financial compensation for fishing / little income opportunity	5.60%
Illegal Fishing	3.20%
High turnover of personnel	3.20%
Profit-sharing	3.20%
Inability to enforce rules	2.40%
Lack of Fisher Institutional Awareness	2.40%
Forest health	2.40%
Food / water	2.40%
Changing Weather	0.80%
Management not local	0.80%
Less Fish	0.80%
More Frequent Meeting Occurrence	0.80%
Promote Local Knowledge	0.80%

Figure 5*Stakeholder diagram**Source: Author's creation*

When reviewing the interview data of both fishers and non-fishers, several themes came up as factors which influence fishers and their relationship with the co-management institutions. Class issues, corruption, and loans were determined as the three largest factors which influence the viability of fisher institutional participation. Slightly over 65% of the total responses belonged to a category that was identified by both fishing and non-fishing stakeholders. As such, only about 35% of total responses were identified by a single group rather than both.

Although the majority of fishers identified threats more closely associated with the functionality of the co-management systems, just under 9% of total responses were of fishers who identified threats more closely tied to their livelihoods, such as forest health, declining fish catch, and issues with food and/or water, with the hope that the co-management institutions would help mitigate these threats. While a small portion of fisher stakeholders are looking to improve their livelihoods, the majority of fishing and non-fishing stakeholders are looking to improve the regulating powers of governing institutions. Non-fishing stakeholders only identified criteria that speak to the functionality of the co-management institutions. This indicates that both groups are aware that further work must be done for the co-management institutions to be successful.

4. Discussion

The results capture responses from fishing and non-fishing stakeholders across four unions. The results are consistent with earlier sections with the separation of single and multi-stakeholder responses. The discussion begins with fisher accounts and attempts to display the linkages and relationships between factors of reach, transparency, and empowerment. Following this, a multi-stakeholder overview focusing on the impacts of social capital, corruption, loans, and knowledge-sharing on small-scale fishers and their relationships with the co-management institutions.

4.1 Fisher accounts

This section discusses fisher accounts as they relate to reach, transparency, and empowerment. These accounts represent and highlight similarities and differences in institutions across all four unions.

4.1.1 Reach, transparency and empowerment

The primary half of this chapter attempts to measure two means of common governance principles in both engagement and transparency in context to the co-management institution in Satkhira. It further attempts to measure the reach of the co-management institutions to better understand how many fishers are actually interacting with the institutions. Finally, this chapter attempts to present links between the concepts of institutional reach with transparency and engagement. Through this chapter, reach was measured to understand general inclusion or introductory inclusion, transparency to understand fisher trust in the institutions, and empowerment to better understand the role of fishers themselves. The measurements and analysis further allowed for an understanding of the first objective of the research project, which was to contextualize and conceptualize co-management in the Sundarbans to ultimately better understand how the in-place systems operate.

Unions which saw lower levels of the institutions reaching them, simultaneously reported lower levels of transparency, as well as engagement in the institutions. In all measurements, all unions followed a similar curve outside of Burigoalini. In all other unions, low levels of reach, transparency, and empowerment were relatively uniform. Burigoalini, the only union with a heightened level of institutional reach, reported higher levels of transparency and engagement. It is important to note that key governing offices responsible for the co-management institutions are in Burigoalini, which likely influenced the increased reach of the institutions.

Burigoalini's comparative success speaks to the value of reach of co-management institution. For a fisher to adequately engage with an institution, the fisher at minimum requires the knowledge of the institution's existence. Through increased reach, fishers have more knowledge about the institutions, which would then increase the transparency of the institutions. Increased institutional transparency will lead to increased empowerment as transparency will allow fishers to more accurately engage with aspects of the institutions which they feel are most beneficial to their lives and livelihoods. Increased empowerment will lead to an increase of communication regarding the effectiveness of an institutions, leading to increased communication reflecting in a higher institutional reach. This promotes a circular relationship between the three factors, which is reflected below in figure 6.

Figure 6

Relationship between reach, transparency, and empowerment in a co-management institution

Source: Author's creation

While singularly, reach, transparency or empowerment cannot describe the entirety of a co-management institution, together they can provide more holistic understanding of the processes within the institutions. For transparency to be empowering, literature points that transparency may need to be paired with a tool, initiative, or something otherwise that would promote the needs of fishers (Orofino et al., 2023). As such, a transparent co-management institution has the potential to prioritize fisher needs beyond an extent which is typically delivered through an institution which lacks transparency. Literature finds that with increased transparency and/or empowerment, fishers are more likely to be willing to comply with institutional regulations in a co-management setting (Bown et al., 2013; Battista et al., 2018). This is backed up by the data revealed through this section, which identifies that unions with lower levels of institutional reach, are shown to have lower levels of institutional transparency, which further allows for lower levels of fisher empowerment.

It should be emphasized that without some form of institutional reach engaging and introducing fishers to the co-management system, they will remain uninformed about the institutions and further be less likely to comply with the institutions. Based on the four unions, a lack of communication or access to information from the institution leads to a lack of empowerment, while increased communication eventually leads to increased empowerment. A lack of information leads to a lack of ability to use the information. A lack of access to regulatory information is a sign of low transparency. Following this logic, a lack of understanding or awareness of the institutions, prevents fishers from participating in the institutions. Increasing the reach that communication and information related to co-management travels would likely increase fisher empowerment, as more fishers would be aware of the institutions and their powers within the institutions.

4.2 Multi-Stakeholder Accounts

This section discusses factors impacting small-scale fishers as related to the co-management institutions identified by both fishing and non-fishing stakeholders to create a holistic understanding of all stakeholder accounts. Several factors were identified across different stakeholder groups, however, four factors stood out as commonly referred to and further focused on in this paper. Social capital, loans, corruption, and knowledge-sharing were determined as the biggest factors which impact fishers' relationships with the co-management institutions.

4.2.1 Class Issues and Lack of Social Capital

Among all stakeholders, social capital was acknowledged as one of the two largest factors which impacts fisher relations with the co-management institutions. Lack of social capital, or issues relating to the social class of fishers, refers to a stakeholder's ability to function in a society based on their social powers. Social capital can be understood in co-management as the social norms, networks, and relationships that harbour a cohesive working environment between all respective stakeholders (Armitage et al., 2008). Co-management institutions may attempt to address social capital and trust and build relationships between stakeholders, however, it is evident the differences amongst stakeholders within the institutions are regularly not addressed to a standard that makes meaningful change to marginalized populations (Fratsea & Papadopoulos, 2022; Chuenpagdee et al., 2013).

In the context of the Sundarbans, a lack of social capital for forest-dependent stakeholders plague them not only in relation to the co-management institutions, but in almost all other measurable aspects of their lives as well. In relation to the co-management institutions, fishers felt that their lack of social status prevented them from engaging meaningfully. Previously established relationships with NGO and governing actors place fishers in a subordinate role.

Pre-existing loans and debts fishers have with NGO stakeholders involved with the co-management institutions impact power dynamics between them the groups. Beyond this, fisher relationships with

governing stakeholders also weigh in favour of the governing stakeholders. This is inherently true when considering that the governing stakeholders are creating and enforcing rules, while the resource-dependent stakeholders choose to follow the rules and is further emphasized when considering bribery. Fishers do not enjoy the social benefits that come with working for an NGO, or the government, and are regularly treated poorly due to their low social status. Beyond this, fishers lack common determinants of upwards social mobility when considering their access to education, healthcare, food, clean water and sanitation. These conditions further prevent them from engaging with the institutions while accelerating fisher poverty. The vast material differences among stakeholders remain unresolved and are reflected in the co-management institutions through its disregard of fisher voices and needs.

As it stands, there is little a fisher can do to improve their material conditions, and they have little financial opportunity. The material conditions of fishers are unlikely to improve if fishers do not receive adequate respect in management processes. Long-term, having a child in school can be a good investment. However, keeping a child in school can prove expensive to maintain for resource dependent people. This is particularly true when considering the role of child labour and the labour time lost at school. A lack of social capital can prove to be an overwhelming hurdle to overcome for many institutions (Plummer & FitzGibbon, 2006). As social capital deals with the complexities of stakeholder relationships, social differences must be adequately acknowledged. Differences between social groups are often deeply ingrained into societies to an extent that is often beyond the capabilities of co-management. It is important to remember that co-management is a governing tool, and not a complete governing solution in itself.

4.2.2 Corruption

Between all stakeholder groups, corruption was determined as one of the two largest factors which impact fisher relationships with the co-management institutions. In this study, corruption is understood as the abuse of or dishonest function of stakeholder powers for personal or wider social benefit. A common example of corruption that was commonly found in interviews was the bribery of forest officers by fishers to access fishing areas. More generally, corruption refers to instances of reported bribery, extortion, rule-breaking or dishonest use of governing tools by governing stakeholders. Fishers spoke to forest officers arresting fishers for fishing in legal fishing zones, among other disputes. As small-scale fishers are among the poorest and most marginalized populations in the world, trade-offs between participating in bribes and potential time spent punished can prove to be significant. As fishers have little means of improving their livelihood situations, the short-term gain for fishers to participate in corruption and pay bribes can often be received as an attractive offer (Foellmi, R., & Oechslin, 2007).

Despite the short-term gain available, the opportunity for fishers to engage in corruption still requires governing actors to first be willing to corruptly behave (Rose-Ackerman, 1997). Literature is divided surrounding what motivates engagement in corruption (Sundstrom, 2019). Older branches of study spoke to anticipated personal gains being the driver for engaging in corruption (Becket & Stigler, 1974; Ades & Di Tella, 1999). Modern branches assume that engagement in corruption is tied to expectations surrounding the roles of other actors participating in the institutions (Dong et al., 2012; Persson et al., 2013). Regardless, corruption remains a major challenge for fisheries co-management institutions internationally (Nunan et al., 2018; Nunan 2020; Rahman & Islam, 2018). Should stakeholder goals and practices be more-so aligned with short-term gain, anticipated personal gains, or in relation to stakeholder expectations and roles, the long-term goal of a sustainable co-management institution may prove to be difficult to realize.

Both attitudes in engaging from the standpoint of a governing actor and complying from the standpoint of fishers need to be addressed should the institutions aim to truly be free of corruption. The ability for both governing and non-governing actors to take advantage of a governing system must be addressed through an adequate justice system. An adequate justice system in the Sundarbans must recognize the relationship

between fisher marginalization and the commodification of the Sundarbans (Siddique, 2023). The current value of fisher labour isn't suitable for fishers to comply with governing order. The failure of a judicial system to recognize this will lead to the persecution of resource-dependent people while simultaneously failing to target drivers in fishers' consumption of corrupt acts.

4.2.3 Loan

The use of microcredit and microloans has spread like wildfire through Bangladesh and become a common practice in the NGO sector. The concept remains controversial. Although it is considered a means of alleviating poverty by many, others argue it to be a debt trap which targets some of the most marginalized populations in the world (Mallik 2024; Mozumder et al., 2024). Microcredit provides credit to users who lack collateral, adequate employment or credit history.

Using a credit system to expense and expedite the growth and development of a local economy makes sense and is a common development strategy. However, if a loan fails to bring back its intended value the loanee will have a reduced ability to pay the loan back. Fishers struggle to receive fair value for their labour and establish tenure rights, they often rent boats, equipment, and fishing spaces while further dealing with bribes and robberies. Their lives are not ignorant of a rising cost of living, while their means to increase household income or access alternative income sources are extremely limited. As such, many fishers turn to microloans, which allows them quick access to funds. Fishers, who already have limited purchasing powers, will likely have no means to pay back a loan which failed to deliver a return on investment. This was evident when reviewing stakeholder data, as it was revealed that ¼ of fishers identified the loans as a barrier which negatively impacts their livelihood and ability to engage with the co-management institutions. Almost all fishers were engaged with at least one loan. While fishers initially take loans to benefit their livelihood practices, it is regular practice for fishers to pay back one loan by taking out another loan.

Loans and credit systems quickly lose their benefits once they sponsor overbearing or unpayable debts. Loans can be beneficial if there is a legitimate means for the loanee to receive a return on investment and if there is a debt revelation strategy. Credit systems built on perpetual debt are not sustainable, and a nation should not want this for its poorest citizens. Microcredit, as it is used, will not positively impact the relationship resource-dependent people have with the resources. It will rather negatively impact on the relationship as the need to pay back the loan increases people's resource-dependency.

4.2.4 Knowledge-Sharing

As different environments will harbour their own respective needs that will require specific focus, co-management stresses the importance of local knowledge systems and knowledge generation (Berkes, 2009; Moller et al., 2004). Knowledge-sharing generally refers to the process of information flow between stakeholders through co-management institutions. While it is common for co-management structures to be top-down in nature, maintaining active communication channels with fishers where they have a speaking role is necessary for a successful co-management institution (Freeman et al., 2018). Existing in a listening role has limited benefits, particularly for already marginalized stakeholders. Communication plays a crucial role in maintaining institutional integrity as it promotes an understanding of institutional goals among all stakeholders while further incorporating the fishers' role in the structures.

In Satkhira, knowledge-sharing was identified in just over 13% of fisher responses, and over 10% of non-fisher stakeholders. Knowledge-sharing typically occurred in VCF meetings, the lowest level of the co-management institutions. Institutional interactions for the most part exist in a top-down orientation. Typically, these interactions were reported as being NGO and governing stakeholders informing fishing stakeholders about statutory order relating to forest management, fishing and other livelihoods. For the most part, fishers felt that they had little space to share their own views and existed in a listening role.

Beyond this, many fishers described the policy that is being shared during the meeting as information that is already known to them and described the institutions as a waste of time. Many fishers shared the sentiment that the institutions did not benefit them and focused on the concerns of governing authorities rather than their concerns as fishers. While the introduction of knowledge-sharing is a crucial element of co-management and a significant step in the development of co-management institutions, without effective two-way communication with co-management institutions it will not be enough to support and understand fisher needs. The state of institutional knowledge-sharing in Satkhira is simultaneously evidence of the development of co-management when compared to past institutions, and that further development is needed in order for effective institutions.

5. Conclusions

This study revealed several factors impacting fisher participation with the co-management institutions in Satkhira. This study identifies reach as a measurement tool useful in contextualizing a co-management institution and further identifies a cyclical relationship between factors of reach, transparency, and empowerment in a co-management context. Beyond that, using both fisher and non-fisher data, this study found that lack of social capital, predatory loan structures, corruption, and knowledge-sharing were the four factors which most impacted fishers' institutional participation. These factors are intertwined with each other and are impossible to fully address independently. Slightly over 65% of the total responses were identified by both fishing and non-fishing stakeholders. Fishers had a slight preference to relate responses back to their livelihoods, while non-fisher stakeholders' responses were more oriented towards the efficiency of the co-management structure.

References

- Ades, A., & Di Tella, R. (1999). Rents, competition, and corruption. *American economic review*, 89(4), 982-993.
- Armitage, D. (2008). Governance and the commons in a multi-level world. *International Journal of the commons*, 2(1), 7-32.
- Azad, K. N., & Azad, K. N. (2022). Current status and chronological development of fisheries and aquaculture in Bangladesh. *Journal of Bioscience and Agriculture Research*, 29(02), 2484-2496.
- Rahman, M. M. (2011). *NUTRIENT CONTENTS OF SOME REPRESENTATIVE SOILS OF GANGES RIVER FLOODPLAIN* (Doctoral dissertation, Khulna University).
- Badola, R., & Hussain, S. A. (2005). Valuing ecosystem functions: an empirical study on the storm protection function of Bhitarkanika mangrove ecosystem, India. *Environmental Conservation*, 32(1), 85-92.
- Barbier, E. B. (2016). The protective service of mangrove ecosystems: A review of valuation methods. *Marine pollution bulletin*, 109(2), 676-681.
- Bangladesh achieves self-sufficiency in four key food items
- Battista, W., Romero-Canyas, R., Smith, S. L., Fraire, J., Effron, M., Larson-Konar, D., & Fujita, R. (2018). Behavior change interventions to reduce illegal fishing. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 5, 403.
- Becker, G. S., & Stigler, G. J. (1974). Law enforcement, malfeasance, and compensation of enforcers. *The Journal of Legal Studies*, 3(1), 1-18.
- Berkes, F. (2009). Evolution of co-management: Role of knowledge generation, bridging organizations and social learning. *Journal of environmental management*, 90(5), 1692-1702.
- Begum, F., de Bruyn, L. L., Kristiansen, P., & Islam, M. A. (2021). Institutionalising co-management activities for conservation of forest resources: Evidence from the Sundarban mangrove forest management of Bangladesh. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 298, 113504.
- Bown, N. K., Gray, T. S., & Stead, S. M. (2013). Co-management and adaptive co-management: Two modes of governance in a Honduran marine protected area. *Marine Policy*, 39(1), 128–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.09.005>
- Chuenpagdee, R., Pascual-Fernández, J. J., Szeliánszky, E., Alegret, J. L., Fraga, J., & Jentoft, S. (2013). Marine protected areas: Re-thinking their inception. *Marine Policy*, 39, 234-240.
- Diba, S. A., Irfanullah, H. M., Selim, S. A., & Raihan, S. T. (2022). *A Situational Analysis of Small-Scale Fisheries in Bangladesh: From Vulnerability to Viability*. V2V Working Paper 2022-01. V2V Global Partnership, University of Waterloo, Canada.
- Didar-UI Islam, S. M., Bhuiyan, M. A., & Ramanathan, A. L. (2015). Climate change impacts and vulnerability assessment in coastal region of Bangladesh: a case study on Shyamnagar Upazila of Satkhira District. *Journal of Climate Change*, 1(1-2), 37-45.
- DOF. 2023. Yearbook of Fisheries Statistics of Bangladesh, 2022-23. Fisheries Resources Survey System (FRSS), Department of Fisheries; Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, 2023. Volume 40; 138p EDITORIAL
- Dong, B., Dulleck, U., & Torgler, B. (2012). Conditional corruption. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 33(3), 609-627.

- Fratsea, L. M., & Papadopoulos, A. G. (2022). Fisheries co-management in the “Age of the commons”: social capital, conflict, and social challenges in the aegean sea. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14578.
- Freeman, E. R., Civera, C., Cortese, D., & Fiandrino, S. (2018). Strategising stakeholder empowerment for effective co-management within fishery-based commons. *British Food Journal*, 120(11), 2631-2644.
- Foellmi, R., & Oechslin, M. (2007). Who gains from non-collusive corruption?. *Journal of development Economics*, 82(1), 95-119.
- Granek, E. F., & Ruttenberg, B. I. (2007). Protective capacity of mangroves during tropical storms: a case study from ‘Wilma’ and ‘Gamma’ in Belize. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 343, 101-105.
- Giri, S., Mukhopadhyay, A., Hazra, S., Mukherjee, S., Roy, D., Ghosh, S., ... & Mitra, D. (2014). A study on abundance and distribution of mangrove species in Indian Sundarban using remote sensing technique. *Journal of coastal conservation*, 18, 359-367.
- Gunjal G.K., (2021). A Study of Climate Change-Induced Migration in the Sundarbans Mangrove Region in the Last Ten Years. <https://cjids.in/volume-v-2021/a-study-of-climate-change-induced-migration-in-the-sundarbans-mangrove-region-in-the-last-ten-years/a-study-of-climate-change-induced-migration-in-the-sundarbans-mangrove-region-in-the-last-ten-years/>
- Hossain, A. (2023). Quantity or quality of fish in a developing country: A hedonic analysis. *Journal of Applied Aquaculture*, 35(2), 394-409.
- International Trade Administration. (2022). *Bangladesh - agriculture sectors*. U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/bangladesh-agriculture-sectors>
- Islam, A. Exploration of Demographic and Basic Household Information with Analyzing Women Rights, Women Security and Domestic Violence of Shyamnagar Upazila, Satkhira.
- Islam, M. M., & Shamsuddoha, M. D. (2018). Coastal and marine conservation strategy for Bangladesh in the context of achieving blue growth and sustainable development goals (SDGs). *Environmental science & policy*, 87, 45-54.
- Islam, S. (2023). Fish Production of Bangladesh, It's Pattern & Impact on GDP. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaf.2020.01.001>
- Mallik, S. K. (2024). Microcredit's effects on household's Bangladeshi perspective on fish producers' earnings and expenses.
- Mozumder, M. M. H., Schneider, P., Islam, M. M., Deb, D., Acharjee, M. R., & Washi, A. M. J. (2024). Bridging the gap: enhancing socio-ecological resilience by breaking the debt cycle among small-scale hilsa fishers in Bangladesh. *Maritime Studies*, 23(1), 10.
- Nunan, F. (2020). The political economy of fisheries co-management: Challenging the potential for success on Lake Victoria. *Global Environmental Change*, 63, 102101.
- Nunan, F., Cepić, D., Yongo, E., Salehe, M., Mbilingi, B., Odongkara, K., ... & Owili, M. (2018). Compliance, corruption and co-management: how corruption fuels illegalities and undermines the legitimacy of fisheries co-management. *International Journal of the Commons*, 12(2), 58-79.
- Orofino, S., McDonald, G., Mayorga, J., Costello, C., & Bradley, D. (2023). Opportunities and challenges for improving fisheries management through greater transparency in vessel tracking. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 80(4), 675-689.

- Persson, A., Rothstein, B., & Teorell, J. (2013). Why anticorruption reforms fail—systemic corruption as a collective action problem. *Governance*, 26(3), 449-471.
- Plummer, R., & FitzGibbon, J. (2006, February). People matter: The importance of social capital in the co-management of natural resources. In *Natural Resources Forum* (Vol. 30, No. 1, pp. 51-62). Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Rahman, M. M., & Islam, N. (2018). Effectiveness of Co-management Approach in the Protected Areas of Sundarbans: A Double-Edged Sword Tools for Biodiversity Conservation. *The Jahangirnagar Review, Part II: Social Sciences*, 42, 53-70.
- Rahman, M. S. (2009). Ecology and management of Sundarban: A rich biodiversity of the world's largest mangrove ecosystem. URL: <http://docs.google.com/viewer>
- Roy, A. K. D., & Alam, K. (2012). Participatory forest management for the sustainable management of the Sundarbans mangrove forest. *American Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 8(5), 549-555.
- Rose-Ackerman, S. (1997). The political economy of corruption. *Corruption and the global economy*, 31(60), 54.
- Saha, C. K. (2015). Dynamics of disaster-induced risk in southwestern coastal Bangladesh: an analysis on tropical Cyclone Aila 2009. *Natural Hazards*, 75(1), 727-754.
- Siddique, M. R. H., Hossain, M., & Rashid, A. M. (2023). The dilemma of prioritizing conservation over livelihoods: Assessing the impact of fishing restriction to the fishermen of the Sundarbans. *Trees, Forests and People*, 11, 100366.
- Shamsuzzaman, M. M., Mozumder, M. M. H., Mitu, S. J., Ahamad, A. F., & Bhyuian, M. S. (2020). The economic contribution of fish and fish trade in Bangladesh. *Aquaculture and Fisheries*, 5(4), 174-181.
- Sundström, A. (2019). Why do people pay bribes? A survey experiment with resource users. *Social Science Quarterly*, 100(3), 725-735.
- The World Bank. (n.d.). Literacy rate, adult male (% of males ages 15 and above) – Bangladesh. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.ADT.LITR.MA.ZS?locations=BD>

Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in an its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

V2V Global Partnership Secretariat
School of Environment, Enterprise and Development,
Faculty of Environment
200 University Avenue West, EV 3
University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, N2L 3G1 Canada
Website: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org
Email: v2vglobalpartnership@gmail.com

V2V WORKING PAPER SERIES

**VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
GLOBAL PARTNERSHIP**

